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THE PEDAGOGICAL COMPONENT OF THE TEXT PHENOMENON IN THE LINGUISTIC EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**Moldir Toiganbekova***Ph.D. Doctoral Candidate,**Abay Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Gulmira Kazhigaliyeva***Professor,**Abay Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

This article is devoted to the study of the pedagogical aspect of the phenomenon of text in the context of the educational process. The key roles and functions of the text as a didactic tool that promotes effective learning and student development are considered. The article analyzes various types of texts used in education, their impact on cognitive processes, the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies. Special attention is paid to methodological approaches to the use of text at various stages of learning, including the selection, adaptation and development of educational text materials. The purpose of this study is to determine the pedagogical significance of the text and to develop practical recommendations for its optimal application to improve the quality of education.

Keywords: pedagogical aspect, the phenomenon of text, teaching, educational process, didactic tool, educational text, reader's literacy, critical thinking.

In modern pedagogical science, in the context of rethinking the role of information and communication in education, the phenomenon of text acquires special significance, going beyond the traditional understanding of a textbook or lecture. Despite the diversity of forms of information presentation (printed, electronic, audiovisual), the pedagogical aspect of text as a holistic phenomenon that retains its invariance requires in-depth and systematic research.

Firstly, the results of the study will help to optimize the processes of selection and creation of educational texts. Identification of key characteristics of a pedagogically effective text and development of corresponding evaluation criteria will help teachers to take a more conscious approach to the selection and adaptation of existing materials, and authors will help to create texts that meet the educational goals and needs of students to the maximum extent. Secondly, the study is aimed at improving the methods of working with text in the linguistic educational process. Identification of effective strategies for interaction between students and text, taking into account its pedagogical potential, will allow teachers to activate the cognitive activity of students, develop their analytical and critical abilities, and also form skills of independent work with information.

The object of this study is the pedagogical aspect of the text phenomenon as a multifaceted phenomenon that determines its role and functions in the educational process. In a broader sense, the object of the study is the process of interaction of students with various types of texts in the educational space and its impact on their cognitive, emotional and personal development, as well as the factors that determine the pedagogical effectiveness of this interaction. The hypothesis of the study is the assumption that a deep understanding of the pedagogical aspect of the text phenomenon and the development of scientifically based approaches to its use in the educational process will significantly increase the

effectiveness of training, will contribute to a deeper assimilation of knowledge, the development of key competencies and the formation of a holistic picture of the world among students.

In the course of our study of the pedagogical aspect of the phenomenon of text in the learning process, a set of complementary methods of analysis was used, including theoretical, practical and quantitative-qualitative approaches.

Our study of the pedagogical aspect of the phenomenon of text involved 30 first-year students of the Abay Kazakh National Pedagogical University, studying in the specialty "Russian Language and Literature". The group was divided into an experimental (15 people) and a control (15 people). Identifying key characteristics of a pedagogically effective text and developing appropriate evaluation criteria will help teachers to take a more conscious approach to selecting and adapting existing materials, and will help authors to create texts that best meet the educational goals and needs of students [1]. The examination of works devoted to both the theoretical foundations of the use of text in pedagogy and practical methods of its application at various stages of training contributes to the formation of a holistic understanding of the phenomenon under study [2,3,4].

As V.A. Sukhomlinsky notes: "Reading is one of the roads leading to wisdom, to the knowledge of life" In the context of pedagogical education, specially selected texts become a tool for understanding pedagogical reality, developing critical thinking and forming readiness for professional activity [5].

The study used a qualitative method with elements of quantitative assessment, based on observation of the educational process and analysis of the results of completing assignments. During the experiment, classes in both groups included work with pedagogical texts from textbooks and methodological manuals. However, in the experimental group, the emphasis was on using texts specially selected and adapted according to the

following criteria: 1) the texts contained descriptions of real pedagogical situations, problems or contradictions, allowed for various interpretations and touched upon the emotional aspects of pedagogical activity; 2) the texts included unfinished plots or questions, described the dynamics of the development of situations, demonstrated cause-and-effect relationships and suggested a variability of possible scenarios; 3) the texts corresponded to the topics studied, reflected modern pedagogical approaches and had practical significance for the future professional activity of students; 4) the language of the texts corresponded to the level of language proficiency of first-year students, the volume was optimal for analysis, the structure was clear, and the texts provided an opportunity for various types of educational work. These criteria were developed in order to ensure the targeted impact of texts on the development of reflective and predictive skills of students in the experimental group.

Students were asked to formulate questions about the text, express their own opinions, argue their position and compare different interpretations. Creative tasks were also used, such as developing options for pedagogical influence based on the studied text or writing short essays-reflections. In the control group, work with pedagogical texts was more traditional in nature and was aimed primarily at assimilating theoretical information and reproducing the content. During the study, we observed the development of the following pedagogically significant skills in students: analytical (the ability to identify a pedagogical problem in a text), reflexive (the ability to comprehend pedagogical situations and one's own pedagogical position) and prognostic (the ability to foresee possible consequences of pedagogical actions). Students in the experimental group demonstrated a more pronounced development of reflexive and prognostic skills compared to students in the control group. They were more active in discussions, analyzed pedagogical situations more deeply and proposed more substantiated solutions, which indicates a positive impact of targeted work with pedagogically oriented texts on the formation of their professional thinking.

The conducted study allowed us to make a number of significant conclusions about the role of text in the pedagogical process. The study period: 21.01.2025 – 10.02.2025. The results of the study convincingly demonstrate the positive impact of the targeted use of pedagogically oriented texts on the development of key professional competencies of future teachers compared to the traditional approach. In the experimental group, where texts selected and adapted taking into account pedagogical goals were used, noticeable progress was observed in all parameters studied.

The study involved first-year students aged 18 to 20. The age composition of both groups was relatively homogeneous, which minimized the impact of this factor on the results of the study. Students in the experimental group demonstrated a higher level of development of reflective skills. They analyzed the proposed pedagogical situations more deeply, more accurately identified pedagogical problems and proposed more diverse and well-founded options for solving them. The

ability to formulate their own pedagogical position and argue for it became more conscious for them. Students in the experimental group demonstrated a significant advantage in all criteria for assessing pedagogical competencies compared to the control group. The choice of assessment criteria in this study is due to their key role in the professional activity of a teacher. Understanding the pedagogical situation is the basis for making adequate pedagogical decisions. Developed reflection allows a teacher to analyze their own activities, identify strengths and weaknesses and adjust their practice. Prognostic skills are necessary for planning the educational process and anticipating possible results of pedagogical influences. The level of understanding of the pedagogical situation was assessed by the ability of students to identify key problems, define the goals and objectives of pedagogical activity, and take into account the context of the situation. Students in the experimental group showed a 13% higher result, which indicates the effectiveness of using texts that focus on the analysis of specific pedagogical cases. The level of development of reflection was assessed by the depth of self-analysis by students of their pedagogical activity and the ability to critically evaluate various approaches. In the experimental group, this indicator was 11% higher, which confirms the influence of texts that stimulate understanding of pedagogical experience. The greatest difference was observed in the level of development of predictive skills. Students in the experimental group showed a 15% higher result, which indicates the effectiveness of using texts that require predicting the consequences of pedagogical decisions. The results obtained confirm the hypothesis that the targeted use of pedagogically oriented texts contributes to a more effective formation of professional competencies of future teachers.

The obtained results confirm that the systematic use of texts focused on pedagogical analysis and reflection is an effective means of developing key professional skills of future teachers. This allows not only to deepen theoretical knowledge, but also to form practical skills in analyzing pedagogical situations and making informed decisions, which is a prerequisite for successful professional activity. Our hypothesis that pedagogically oriented texts contribute to the development of analytical, reflective and predictive skills was confirmed. The development and implementation of such texts in the educational process is a promising direction for improving pedagogical training.

The results of the study clearly confirm the importance of the targeted use of pedagogically oriented texts in the educational process. A logical question arises: what mechanisms exactly ensure such effectiveness?

The analysis of pedagogical texts, specially selected and adapted for the development of professional competencies, suggests that they are rich in problem situations that require pedagogical understanding. Students do not just get acquainted with theoretical material, but are immersed in the context of real pedagogical tasks. The use of pedagogically oriented texts allows students to see the versatility of pedagogical activity

and the relationship between its various aspects. Consideration of specific situations, description of the experience of practicing teachers and analysis of pedagogical research contribute to the formation of a holistic view of the profession. Students learn to understand the context of pedagogical decisions, take into account the characteristics of students and the educational environment, which is an important condition for effective professional activity. We believe that the analysis of such texts helps students better understand and interpret pedagogical phenomena, developing their analytical and predictive skills. When students see the practical significance of the material studied and its connection with future professional activity, their motivation for learning increases. They realize that mastering pedagogical texts is not just an educational task, but an important stage in professional development.

The conducted study convincingly proves that the targeted selection and use of pedagogically oriented texts are not just a useful methodological technique, but a powerful tool for improving the quality of pedagogical education. The results of the experimental study clearly demonstrate the prospects of this approach. There is noticeable progress in the development of key professional competencies of future teachers, confirmed not only by quantitative indicators, but also by a qualitative analysis of their activities and reflection. Data analysis showed that pedagogically rich texts, acting as a kind of "cases" and incentives for reflection, contribute to a deeper understanding of pedagogical processes, the development of reflective abilities and the formation of predictive skills in students. The study also showed that the use of such texts facilitates the process of forming a professional identity and motivation for pedagogical activity. This is especially relevant in

the context of constantly changing requirements for a modern teacher.

In this article, we have considered the pedagogical aspect of the phenomenon of text as a fundamental element of the educational process. Based on the analysis, the following main conclusions can be made. Pedagogically meaningful use of text is a key factor in increasing the effectiveness of learning and the comprehensive development of the personality of students. Taking into account the didactic, content, structural, linguistic and methodological characteristics of the text allows us to maximize its educational potential. Systematic study and improvement of approaches to the use of text in the educational process is an important area of pedagogical science, both theory and practice, contributing to improving the quality of education in general.

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